

ECLIPSE OF THE SOUL AND OF LAW: A PHILOSOPHICAL CRITIQUE OF THE PROTECTION OF PORNOGRAPHY BY THE PRINCIPLE OF FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19926649

Bruno Zampier

Graduated in Law from the Curitiba University Center, postgraduate in Criminal Law and Criminal Procedure from the Brazilian Academy of Constitutional Law, Master in Philosophy from the Federal University of Paraná, Lawyer and professor of Criminal Law and Philosophy of Law at the Campo Real University Center and the University of the Midwest (Unicentro) in Guarapuava-PR.

ABSTRACT

Technological development has facilitated and universalized access to pornography through the internet. Following Ronald Dworkin's thought, both the jurisprudence of the Federal Supreme Court and the majority of legal doctrine consider that obscenity is protected by the principle of social adequacy and freedom of expression. This article presents and discusses this conception, contested by the conservative approach of John M. Finnis and Roger Scruton, who sustain a secular-based sexual morality. The method employed is bibliographic and jurisprudential review. It is concluded that pornography, far from being merely a harmless activity of private life, disseminates a dehumanized conception of sexuality, violating several legal provisions: it generates harm to character formation, sexual education, and the construction of affective family bonds. Such consequence is not sheltered by freedom of expression, since it violates the principle of human dignity.

Keywords: Freedom of expression. Pornography. Dehumanization of sexuality.

I. INTRODUCTION

From a legal standpoint, we can divide pornography into two main categories: legal and illegal. The first is that which, (a) although subject to some restrictions, is widely disseminated, consumed, and commercialized. The second (b) constitutes criminal conduct. Within this second category, we can further observe a subdivision: (bi) pornography that is criminal according to the law and considered unacceptable by jurisprudence and doctrine, and (b-ii) pornography that is criminal or illegal according to the law but tolerated by jurisprudence and

doctrine. Within the first subdivision (bi) we find the forms of pornography involving children and adolescents ², the unauthorized recording of sexual activity ³, and the unauthorized dissemination of rape scenes ⁴. Within the second subdivision (b-ii) we find the crimes of obscene acts ⁵ and obscene writings or objects ⁶, as well as administrative restrictions on the presentation of such content to children and adolescents in publications, shows, and audiovisual broadcasts ⁷.

In this article, we present a philosophical critique of pornography in general, based on the analytical theory of Roger Scruton and the Thomistic natural law of John M. Finnis and Robert P. George, demonstrating that not only criminal pornography deserves repression, but also that which is currently tolerated.

Thus, in Chapter X we will present a summary of the legal provisions on pornography as well as the jurisprudential understanding. We will see that, for the Brazilian Supreme Court (STF), administrative reprimands against radio and television channels that may present obscene programming outside of appropriate hours would constitute a violation of the principle of freedom of the press and expression. This is a position similar to that of the US Supreme Court, and also to that of Ronald Dworkin .

Implicitly, though quite evidently, the Supreme Court considers the prohibition of access to pornography by children and adolescents a matter of subjective morality, regarding which the State lacks the legitimacy to impose punishments and sanctions on media outlets without incurring unconstitutionality. Such a task would then fall exclusively to parents or guardians, as a mere option, according to their personal opinions. It should be noted that the Supreme Court's decision, we emphasize from the outset, does not even address pornography freely disseminated on the internet, limiting itself to granting virtually unrestricted freedom of expression of obscenity to television channels, radio, and public performance venues.

In contrast to this subjectivist view, the most recent studies conducted by psychologists, psychiatrists, neurologists, philosophers, and jurists clearly demonstrate that pornography has deleterious effects, not only on adults, but especially on children and adolescents. These are

²Law 11.829 of 2008 inserted into the Statute of Children and Adolescents (Law 8.069/1990) several criminal offenses (Articles 240, 241, 241-A, 241-B, 241-C, 241-D, 241-E) that criminalize the conduct of producing, supplying, selling, etc., pornographic videos and photographs involving minors. Two of these crimes (Article 240 §1 and 241-B) were included in the list of heinous crimes (Law 8.072/1990 – Article 1, sole paragraph, item VII) by Law 14.811/2024.

³In this case, the crime involves a person over 18 years of age. This crime was added to the Penal Code, Article 216-B, by Law 13.772/2018.

⁴Article 218-C of the Penal Code, inserted by Law 13.718/2018.

⁵Article 233 of the Penal Code.

⁶Article 244 of the Penal Code.

⁷Article 74, sole paragraph, of the Statute of Children and Adolescents

clinical, statistical, and empirical data that demonstrate that traditional sexual morality, which condemns pornography, has an objective foundation in human nature. However, our objective is not to discuss specifically the scientific evidence of the harmful effects of pornography⁸, but to demonstrate how traditional sexual morality is in harmony with the most recent scientific conclusions. In this third chapter, we aim to confront the subjectivism of progressive sexual morality – whose great exponent in the legal world is Ronald Dworkin – with traditional morality, according to the analytical and conservative philosophy of Roger Scruton and the Thomistic natural law of John M. Finnis and Robert P. George, theorists of the New Natural Law⁹.

Understanding the meaning of sexual desire in human beings, and its importance in character formation, allows for a reasonable justification of the traditional restrictions on pornography already provided for in legislation. Thus, objective limits are established on the freedom of expression of the obscene. These limits, far from violating the democratic principle, actually strengthen it, insofar as they promote a view of sexuality that allows the perception of the other as a human being, possessing rights and worthy of respect, and not as a mere object of libidinal satisfaction.

II. Pornography in Law and in the Jurisprudence of the Supreme Federal Court

When we analyze Brazilian legislation concerning obscenity, we observe a normative antinomy: on the one hand, Article 234 of the Penal Code criminalizes the distribution and sale – among various other conducts – of any obscene object¹⁰. In harmony with the penal code, the Statute of Children and Adolescents (Law 8.069/1990) provides a series of measures to prevent children and adolescents from accessing obscene material:

⁸ Readers interested in scientific evidence regarding the harmful effects of pornography on neurological development, sexual health, and psychological health can find a research guide in EBERSTADT, Mary; LAYDEN, Mary Anne. **The Social Costs of Pornography**. São Paulo: Quadrante, 2019.

⁹ This is a contemporary Thomistic-based natural law school of thought, which includes, among others, John M. Finnis and Germain Grisez.

¹⁰ Article 234 - To make, import, export, acquire or possess, for the purpose of trade, distribution or public display, any obscene writing, drawing, painting, print or object:

Penalty - imprisonment for six months to two years, or a fine.

Sole paragraph - The same penalty applies to anyone who:

I - sells, distributes or exposes for sale or to the public any of the objects referred to in this article;

II - performs, in a public place or a place accessible to the public, a theatrical performance or film screening of an obscene nature, or any other spectacle of the same nature;

III - performs, in a public place or a place accessible to the public, or via radio, an audition or recitation of an obscene nature.

- a) It requires those responsible for public shows to post information at the entrance of the venue about the nature of the performance and the age range indicated in the classification certificate (Art. 74, sole paragraph);
- b) Radio and television stations, during the time recommended for children and young people, must present educational, artistic, cultural or informative content (Art. 76);
- c) Video rental companies – a practice now defunct – are prohibited from selling or renting material unsuitable for minors, in violation of age ratings (Art. 77);
- d) Magazines and publications containing inappropriate material must be sold in sealed packaging, with a warning about the content (Art. 78);
- e) Publishers must cover covers with obscene messages or images using opaque packaging (Art. 78, sole paragraph);
- f) In turn, “magazines and publications intended for children and young people [...] must respect the ethical and social values of the individual and the family” (Art. 79).

Regarding radio and television programming, age rating classifications are regulated by ordinances from the Ministry of Justice and Public Security. Currently, this classification can be found in the "Practical Audiovisual Guide ¹¹," a booklet with age ratings for audiovisual works (television, cinema, *streaming*, video games, etc.). Here the contradictions begin. Contrary to the provisions of the Penal Code and the Statute of the Child and Adolescent, according to this document, the age rating is defined as follows:

- a) From the age of 12, it is possible to see scenes of “[...] obscenity, [...] overvaluation of physical beauty and consumerism, and psychological violence. It is permitted to show sexual appeal, caressing or innuendo, vulgar language or language with sexual content, masturbation, veiled nudity, and simulated sex.”
- b) From the age of 14 onwards, “it is possible to see scenes of abortion, [...] sexual exploitation [...] nudity, prostitution, sexual intercourse and vulgarity”;
- c) From the age of 16, "it may involve acts of pedophilia, hate crimes, rape or sexual coercion, mutilation, suicide, torture and gratuitous violence";
- d) From the age of 16, "it can involve acts of pedophilia, hate crimes, rape or sexual coercion, mutilation, suicide, torture and gratuitous violence".
- e) From the age of 18 onwards, "content exclusively intended for adults, and may include themes of violence and cruelty, explicit sex, complex or highly impactful sexual situations."

The doctrine, also out of step with the precepts of the Statute of Children and Adolescents, almost unanimously, instead of recognizing the antinomy and invoking the

¹¹ Available at: https://www.gov.br/mj/pt-br/assuntos/seus-direitos/classificacao-1/paginas-classificacao-indicativa/CLASSINDAUDIOVISUAL_Guia_27042022versaofinal.pdf Accessed on March 7, 2025.

protection of the best interests of the minor, proclaims the need to repeal the provisions of the Penal Code. The disregard of the authorities and a supposed tolerance of society towards the constant exposure to obscenity leads legal scholars to opine in favor of the extinction of penal sanctions for such conduct. Cezar Roberto Bitencourt summarizes this opinion well:

[...] we are faced with the classification of an outdated crime, superseded by the evolution of customs and, especially, admitted, accepted and even regulated by the Public Authorities, who benefit from 'obscene writing, drawing, painting, print or any object' by charging fees and taxes, filling, as they like to do, the coffers of the National Treasury, indifferent to a supposed public immorality or, in this case, to the criminal nature of such activities."¹²

Citing the principle of social adequacy – according to which socially tolerated conduct does not merit penal intervention – Guilherme de Souza Nucci presents the same opinion, highlighting that “constitutional norms must be interpreted in light of the Federal Constitution”¹³. Similarly, Rogério Sanches Cunha¹⁴ argues that, for “the configuration of the crime, an offense against public morality is essential, which no longer occurs” and, therefore, “effective punishment has become uncommon”.

It is also interesting to note the absence, in the Practical Audiovisual Guide, of any regulation regarding pornography disseminated through the internet. Similarly, none of the consulted legal scholars comment on the free distribution of pornographic material via the internet. In the most recent jurisprudence of the higher courts, in turn, there is also no ruling on the websites of the Superior Court of Justice or the Supreme Federal Court regarding the free dissemination of pornography on the internet¹⁵. By way of illustration, on October 1, 1968, the Supreme Federal Court considered a case involving the dissemination of pornographic material. This is Habeas Corpus Appeal (RHC) No. 64695, reported by then-Minister Themistocles Cavalcanti, who at the time stated: “the constitutional right to free expression of thought does not exclude criminal punishment, nor administrative repression of printed, photographed, broadcast or disseminated material by any means, for pornographic or obscene dissemination, under the terms and form of the law. [...]”. Almost twenty years later, in 1987, the court denied a Habeas Corpus petition seeking to halt a police investigation into the distribution of obscene posters related to pornographic films.

¹²BITENCOURT, Cezar Roberto. *Treatise on Criminal Law*, Vol. 4: Special Part. 3rd ed. São Paulo: Saraiva, 2008, p. 88.

¹³NUCCI, Guilherme de Souza. *Annotated Penal Code*. 2nd ed. São Paulo: Revista dos Tribunais, 2002, p. 89.

¹⁴CUNHA, Rogério Sanches. *Criminal Law – Special Part*. Vol. 3. 2nd ed. São Paulo: Revista dos Tribunais, 2009, p. 259.

¹⁵Except in cases of child pornography (as stipulated in the ECA), and those criminal offenses already mentioned in the Penal Code.

RHC 64965 Judging Body : First Panel - Rapporteur: Justice MOREIRA ALVES - Judgment: 08/18/1987 - Publication: 10/16/1987 - Summary
HABEAS CORPUS. DISPLAY OF POSTERS RELATED TO FILMS DEEMED OBSCENE. IN THIS CASE, THERE IS NO LACK OF JUST CAUSE FOR THE DISMISSAL OF THE POLICE INVESTIGATIONS, AS THE CHARGE CONSTITUTES, IN THEORY, A CRIME. ORDINARY APPEAL DENIED.

In 2016, the understanding changed completely. Asked to rule on the airing of programs outside of designated times, the Supreme Federal Court determined that prohibiting broadcasts on open television channels constitutes prior censorship¹⁶. In that case, Minister Dias Toffoli voted to uphold the fine for broadcasters that do not display the age rating of their programming, but decided that if a broadcaster does in fact violate the rating and airs obscene scenes at an inappropriate time, it should not be fined or suspended, as this would constitute a violation of the fundamental right to freedom of the press and expression. During the oral arguments, the aforementioned minister stated the following:

Mr. President, "(...) the public authorities should not, in their eagerness to protect the supposed greater legal good, intervene, censor or tell parents and guardians whether a particular program meets, or does not meet, moral standards." Mr. President, "(...) the public authorities should not, in their eagerness to protect the supposed greater legal good, intervene, censor or tell parents and guardians whether a particular program meets, or does not meet, moral standards." I have already said here, when judging other matters, that the time has come to stop systematically thinking that the people should be tutored by the State, or that the people lack the capacity for discernment, or that the Brazilian people, due to social conditions, would not have the dignity, as human beings, to know how to make their personal and individual choices, to exercise their freedom, needing a guide, an agent who imports their will.

In this respect, according to the minister, it is the State's responsibility to provide parents with the tools to prevent their minor children from watching inappropriate content, but only if they so choose. Since there are no sanctions for either parents or media outlets, the release of obscene content to minors becomes lawful. Therefore, if they deem it appropriate or irrelevant, parents can indeed allow their children access to pornography. In other words, the inappropriateness of pornography as an element of moral development is a matter of mere opinion, as it would be a private matter.

However, we can find other legal incompatibilities in this new understanding when we observe the Maria da Penha Law, and the objectives and purposes of the education of children and adolescents, especially with regard to sex education. The Maria da Penha Law establishes

¹⁶ Direct Action of Unconstitutionality No. 2404. Available at: <https://portal.stf.jus.br/processos/detalhe.asp?incidente=1902202> Accessed on: March 10, 2025.

guidelines incompatible with pornography. First, because the pornographic industry induces and instigates women to commercialize their sexuality, which, according to the aforementioned law, constitutes a form of sexual violence: “Art. 7º The following are forms of domestic and family violence against women, among others: [...] III - sexual violence, understood as any conduct that coerces her to [...] commercialize or use, in any way, her sexuality [...]”. Secondly, and even more conflicting with the new understanding of the Supreme Federal Court (STF), because among the public policy guidelines established to modify socio-cultural patterns of behavior based on prejudice and the idea that women are inferior, we find the duty of respect in the media, through the curbing of stereotypical roles that violate the dignity of women:

Article 8. Public policy aimed at curbing domestic and family violence against women shall be implemented through a coordinated set of actions by the Union, the States, the Federal District, and the Municipalities, as well as non-governmental actions, guided by the following principles: [...]
III - Respect, in the media, for the ethical and social values of the individual and the family, in order to curb stereotypical roles that legitimize or exacerbate domestic and family violence, in accordance with the provisions of item III of article 1, item IV of article 3 and item IV of article 221 of the Federal Constitution;

How pornography violates the ethical values of the individual and the family becomes a fundamental question. A possible answer can be found in the Brazilian National Curriculum Base (BNCC), which establishes the objectives and competencies to be developed in the sexual education of children and adolescents. It acknowledges that emotional issues are inseparable from sexuality, also involving the need to understand the respect due to others, including their mental health.

The aim is for students, upon completing elementary school, to be able to understand the organization and functioning of their bodies, as well as interpret the physical and emotional changes that accompany adolescence and recognize the impact these changes can have on self-esteem and body confidence. It is also fundamental that they are able to take a leading role in choosing positions that represent self-care for their own bodies and respect for the bodies of others, from the perspective of comprehensive care for physical, mental, sexual, and reproductive health.¹⁷

Among the skills to be developed, for example, with 8th-grade students, we find the explicit recognition of the multiple dimensions of sexuality: “EF08CI11 Select arguments that highlight the multiple dimensions of sexuality.” human (biological, sociocultural, affective and ethical). Therefore, it is in the interest of parents and society to make young people aware that

¹⁷ National Common Curricular Base. Available at: <http://basenacionalcomum.mec.gov.br/images/BNCC_EI_EF_110518_versaofinal_site.pdf>

intimate relationships, for example, involve not only the body, but a complex whole to which we must be attentive and cautious: a good physical appearance can hide a difficult or even violent personality; a quick or superficial knowledge of the partner may be enough to arouse libido, but ignores the subjective dimension. Therefore, elevating sexual desire and physical appearance as decisive criteria for establishing a relationship (even a sporadic one) can have negative consequences. The awareness that intimate relationships involve more than just a body is a requirement for building stable and secure relationships, and that experiencing the dramas of betrayal, separation, and divorce is a setback that harms not only the various aspects of an individual's life (mental and physical health, work and study performance, etc.) but also those around them (especially parents and children, siblings and friends). It is even more serious when it results in crimes such as threats, sexual violence, assaults, and femicide. All of this is part of the character education that must be provided, by parents and society, based on human dignity, solidarity and mutual respect, and which is essential for the integration of sexuality as an aspect of human well-being.

Pornography not only hinders such objectives, but also completely subverts the meaning of true character, sexuality, and relationship education. It impoverishes and distorts the meaning of human sexuality, objectifying men and women, stripping them of their status as persons, and elevating appearance and superficial sexual desire as decisive criteria for intimate contact. In short, it is the antithesis of sex education.

This self-evident assumption that human sexuality has multiple dimensions is prominently featured in the conservatism of Roger Scruton and Robert P. George, for whom secular sexual morality is based on objective characteristics of human nature. Pornography, by portraying only the physical dimension of this sexuality, corrupts the meaning of human relationships, disseminating a stereotypical image of women (and also men), harming the sexual education of children and adolescents. It is not, therefore, a mere matter of subjective opinion for parents or guardians. The objective foundations of this philosophical justification of traditional sexual morality that condemns pornography, completely ignored in the opinion of the Supreme Court justices, are what we will see in the next section.

III. Sexual Morality as an Extension of the Principle of Human Dignity

For Ronald Dworkin, controlling pornography would be incompatible with liberal political morality¹⁸. Freedom, a paradigm of Modern Law (post-French Revolution), is based on the principle of the dignity of the human person, which, under the influence of Kantian thought, elevated the autonomy of the individual will as the intangible core of personality and the determining factor of every moral act. This approach applied to pornography, however, is merely formalistic and superficial, limiting the analysis of obscenity – by judges, ministers, and legal scholars – to its voluntariness, neglecting the essence of its object: the reduction of the human person to an objectified body. Considered an optional element of sexuality in general, pornography is protected, in the contemporary era, as a subjective right.

In traditional morality, sexuality is emphasized as a relationship of mutual acceptance, aimed at procreation and perpetual fidelity within marriage. This mutual acceptance consummated in the sexual act presupposes the prior recognition of the other as a person: a complex involving body and soul, or, in anthropological terms, an objectivity and a subjectivity.

Normal desire is an interpersonal emotion. Its goal is the free and mutual surrender that also constitutes the union of two individuals, you and I – through our bodies, of course, but not only as bodies. Normal desire is a response given from person to person, a response that seeks the individuality that this provides. Objects can be replaced; subjects cannot¹⁹.

Roger Scruton finds in this the basis for a distinction between erotic art and pornography. The former, exemplified by Titian's *Venus*, consists of the representation of the embodied person – the incarnation – while the latter manifests an interest in the body exclusively. Hence, sexual desire – an inherent part of human nature – acquires its moral force by recognizing in the other their multiple existential dimensions, respecting what in legal language we call the principle of the dignity of the human person. On the other hand, sexual desire becomes immoral, that is, obscene or pornographic, when it cuts off the person's corporeal dimension and disregards their subjectivity. The woman – or even the man – in pornography is not a person: it is a body to be exploited for the libidinous delight of the spectator. They are objects and, as such, replaceable. Scruton, drawing on Kant's categorical imperative, sees a similarity with slavery: "like slavery, pornography is the negation of the

¹⁸DWORKIN, Ronald. **A Matter of Principle**. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 2001, p. 497 et seq.

¹⁹SCRUTON, Roger. *Beauty*. São Paulo: É Realizações, 2013, p. 169.

human subject, a way of ignoring the moral requirement that free beings treat themselves as ends in themselves."

This traditional understanding of sexuality, labeled as an irrational and arbitrary taboo, actually stems from a self-evident assumption, yet one largely neglected by the post-sexual revolution mentality: human relationships – especially those involving sexual desire – encompass a complex whole, composed of personality traits, desires, and feelings. A sexual act in which the subjectivity of another is disregarded becomes immoral because it strips the other of their complex condition as a person, reducing them to their body.

In true desire, what I want is the other, the other himself. But the other is only real in his freedom and is thus falsified by every attempt to represent him as an object. Therefore, desire seeks the freedom of the other, in order to appropriate him as its own. The lover, who desires to possess the other's body only if, and to the extent that, the other possesses him in himself, is then trapped in a contradiction. His desire is fulfilled only by compelling the other to identify with his body – to lose his for-itself in the in-itself of the flesh. But then, what is possessed is precisely not the freedom of the other, but only the shell of freedom – an abjured freedom.²⁰

By inciting fantasy in a purely empirical and mechanistic way, pornography confines sexuality to the narrow limits of physical sensation, and obscures the understanding of human relationships on a subjective level.

Fantasy fills our thoughts with a sense of the obscene, and orgasm ceases to be about possessing the other and becomes the expenditure of energy on their depersonalized body. [...] The other, in fact, is not of intrinsic interest to me, and serves only as my opportunity for individual pleasure.²¹

This stance towards sexuality, in its most nefarious consequence, is clearly revealed in what we call rape: the violation of human dignity through the disregard of the person, that is, in disregard of their internal elements. Rape is a sexual act in which the subjectivity of another has been dissolved so that *Eros* can be consummated in a power relationship. For the rapist, the psychic state of his victim is of no interest, as long as he can extract pleasure from her body. Therefore, the work of the Marquis de Sade, in which children and women are tortured, raped, and murdered for the sadist's delight, is the "ultimate logical possibility of pornography: the annihilation of the body" (HUNT, 1999, p. 36). The reduction of the other to an objectified body inevitably leads to the procession of rape, abuse, violence, and the very death of the person-object used.

²⁰SCRUTON, Roger. Thinkers of the New Left. São Paulo: É Realizações, 2014, p. 267.

²¹SCRUTON, Roger. Sexual Desire: A Philosophical Investigation. Campinas/SP: Vide Editorial, 2016, p. 466.

This is why, in pornography, the concrete violence of a real rape is eliminated without losing the aesthetics of a sexual relationship based on the extermination of subjectivity: therein lies a serious psychic and behavioral similarity with rape. It thus generates pleasure based on the feeling that the parties consented to the dissolution of their self, instead of reaffirming it in an intimate and private relationship of mutual acceptance. The sadistic pleasure, typical of a relationship of authority, power, and control, is combined with sexual pleasure to the point of climax. For the images in videos or photographs do not truly convey subjectivity, but only its appearance.

This means that love and respect for human complexity are obstacles to pornographic pleasure. Therefore, the rapist's libido is solely a delight in the power he exerts over the other. In pornography, the exercise of this power does not necessarily require an aggressive scene: the relationship of objectification and submission occurs automatically through the reduction of the other to their body. It is in the very nature of pornography, therefore, to stimulate "the interest in seeing people reduced to their bodies, objectified like animals, reified and obscenized."²² This is also the conclusion of Robert P. George, professor of philosophy of law at Princeton University:

[...] this is in the area of wholly loveless, affectionless sex. The sexuality it portrays and invites is thoroughly depersonalized; the passion it appeals to is the desire for the possession of someone's body without any interest in the personality in which, in ordinary life, a body belongs. [...] the magazine presents a pervasive 'objectification' of the erotic experience and the female in particular. The erotic activity is reduced, in graphic detail, to its physical components, and the participants are viewed as instruments for the production of pleasurable sensations²³

Since obscenity encourages viewers to enjoy sexual pleasure without experiencing genuine human relationships, with their difficulties, dramas, and disappointments, it ultimately creates an environment where utilitarianism in sexual matters is incorporated as the sole criterion for personal fulfillment and satisfaction.

Pornography then promotes the image of the "woman-as-object," very likely the most depraved and pernicious form of stereotypical role imposed on women, completely out of step with the Maria da Penha Law, mentioned in the previous section. According to Robert P. George, women, whether children or adults, are precisely the greatest victims of a society that promotes pornography.

²²SCRUTON, Roger. *Beauty*. São Paulo: É Realizações, 2013, p. 176.

²³GEORGE, Robert P. In *Defense of Natural Law*. Oxford: University Press, 2004, p. 188.

I have no doubt that women and girls get the worst of it in a society in which pornography flourishes. Even when pornography depicts women in dominant and powerful, as opposed to subordinate and humiliating, roles, the understands and self-understandings, the provisions and feelings, the sentiments and sensibilities it promotes leads to a 'cultural structure', as Dworkin says, where sexuality lacks dignity and beauty. In the context of such a cultural structure in the real world of male and female sexual psychology and relationships, women and girls are bound to suffer even more than men and boys. Women, for example, are more likely to be abandoned and left unsupported by their sexual partners. They are overwhelmingly more likely to be 'traded in' for younger and sleeker models, even by 'respectable' husbands.

Therefore, any project to promote women's dignity that fails to acknowledge the evils of pornography is doomed to never be effective: the potentiation of selfish and fetishistic mentalities regarding sexuality through pornography is what could very aptly be called "rape culture," something incompatible with a society interested in building a safe environment for everyone, especially children and women.

This construction is complex and delicate, depending on a joint effort for the education of young people. It necessarily needs to involve society, the State, the school, and the family. Therefore, John M. Finnis concludes that the State should adopt measures to help parents educate their children, including on sexual matters.

The fact is that human rights can only be safely enjoyed in certain types of environment – a context or structure of mutual respect, trust, and understanding; an environment that is physically healthy and in which the weak can live without fear of the whims of the strong. [...] If sexuality is a powerful force that can only be integrated with other aspects of personality and human well-being with great difficulty and always precariously [...] and if, moreover, human sexual psychology tends to view other people as physical objects of desire and potential sexual release and gratification, and as mere items in a classification of erotic taste, rather than as whole persons with sensitivities, repressions, and personal and individual life plans, then there are reasons to encourage an environment in which children can be raised (and parents helped, rather than hindered, in the task of raising them) in such a way that they are relatively free from external subjection to a selfish, impulsive, or depersonalized sexuality.²⁴

Contrary to this ideal, pornography *glamorizes* and even instigates predatory sexual behavior. At a less serious level, as has been observed in several studies²⁵, it can generate introspection, social withdrawal, and depression, without posing a risk to others in most cases. But Scruton has no doubt that pornography has considerable potential to actually create

²⁴FINNIS, John. *Natural Law and Natural Rights*. São Leopoldo/RS: Unisinos, 2007, p. 212.

²⁵ Links to over two hundred scientific articles on the harms of pornography can be found here: <https://vicioempornografiacomoparar.com/pesquisas/>

criminals: "The harmless masturbator with a camera can at any moment transform into a desperate rapist with a weapon." ²⁶For fantasy that encounters no obstacles in moral rationality will soon assume the position of guiding criterion for behavior in the real world.

The "reality principle" that governs the normal sexual act is a principle of personal encounter, which commands us to respect the other person and also the sanctity of their body as the tangible expression of another self. The world of fantasy obeys no rules and is governed by monstrous myths and illusions that are at war with the human world – illusions, for example, in which women desire to be raped, in which children are awakened to give and receive the most intense sexual pleasure, in which violence is not an affront but an affirmation of a natural right.²⁷

A social order based on principles of fraternity, human dignity, and which has "personal love as its goal and fulfillment" ²⁸cannot therefore be neutral or tolerant of obscenity. While traditional sex education may have been exaggerated and even caricatured in certain aspects, the fact remains that, in general, it was "more faithful to human nature than the libertarian culture that succeeded it" ²⁹.

However, Scruton disagrees with the extreme idea that obscenity should be criminalized ³⁰. This position is also defended by John Finnis and is in accordance with the modern conception according to which Criminal Law is the *last resort*. *The rationale* behind social control is that, since the education (including sex education) and moral development of children and adolescents has been constitutionally established as a duty of the family and the State, as well as the protection of women through *integrated measures* ³¹aimed at cultural reform to curb and eliminate discriminatory behaviors, the conclusion that pornography constitutes an obstacle to legal guidelines and regulations, deserving restrictions and limitations, is inevitable.

III.1 The Parental Control Argument: yet another burden for the victim

To conclude this point, it is necessary to comment on a response frequently presented as a solution for parents who wish to prevent their children's access to pornography: it is often stated that access to pornography by children and adolescents can be curbed by parents through Parental Controls, that is, filters that block access to websites with inappropriate content. This

²⁶SCRUTON, Roger. *Sexual Desire: A Philosophical Inquiry*. Campinas/SP: Vide Editorial, 2016, p. 466.

²⁷SCRUTON, Roger. **Sexual Desire: A Philosophical Investigation**. Campinas/SP: Vide Editorial, 2016, p. 467.

²⁸Idem.

²⁹Idem.

³⁰Idem.

³¹This expression is used in the Maria da Penha Law, as we will see.

is true. However, this suggestion burdens parents with an additional element for controlling their children and grants broad freedom of dissemination to pornographic websites, contradicting the constitutional guidelines that establish that the family is the basis of society and has special protection from the State (Article 226 of the Federal Constitution). Similarly, it contradicts provisions of the ECA (Articles 17 and 18), as already cited, which impose on everyone the duty to preserve the psychic and moral development of children and adolescents. Furthermore, pornography is recognized as an instrument of perversion used by pedophiles to convince children to engage in sexual activity, which even constitutes a crime under the ECA (Article 241-D, I). Now, if the family is the foundation of society and enjoys special protection from the State, and if the upbringing of young people is the responsibility of the whole society, then any conduct that harms them should at least be restricted. Even if we recognize that a complete ban on the dissemination of pornographic material could harm individual freedom, the broad freedom granted to obscene websites and programming on broadcast television, burdening the family with the duty to block them, is not justified.

An analogy clarifies this violation of equality: just as the "polluter-pays" principle prevails in Environmental Law, according to which whoever pollutes must bear the costs of environmental recovery and preservation, the same should apply to pornography. Although obscenity is of interest to many individuals, the fact is that it contributes nothing to the promotion of the common good; on the contrary, it distorts the meaning of human relations. That is, companies operating in the production of pornographic material—websites, magazines, studios—should be burdened, for example, with heavy taxation and the obligation to create mechanisms to effectively control access to their content. A strong tax burden could force websites to require payment for access. Such measures would be in perfect accordance with the guidelines of the Statute of Children and Adolescents (ECA) and the Maria da Penha Law and would not violate individual freedom, but only delimit it, which is perfectly justifiable and desirable, considering that pornography in no way promotes the common good, but on the contrary, constitutes a harmful and even dangerous product in some aspects. It should be noted that even agriculture, essential to the economy, to food and therefore to the common good, suffers limitations through the polluter-pays principle, and there is no reason for the pornographic industry to be privileged with unrestricted freedom.

IV. CONCLUSION

In times of extremely high rape rates and rampant pornography on the internet, it is fitting to conclude our article with a reflection on sex education in schools, which is seen as one of the solutions to combat sexual violence.

True sex education is extremely important, and it substantially includes defining the criteria and principles of a healthy relationship, where both parties are committed to the dignity and well-being of the other to the highest degree. It's not about saying that the victim of violence is responsible for the acts of the rapist or abuser, but about equipping them with criteria and principles that constitute true weapons against sexual violence. Because every action carries some risk: driving, eating, climbing a mountain, swimming, traveling, sunbathing, playing sports. For each of these actions, there is a code of rules and principles to follow, enshrined in the customs and practices of ancestors, capable of mitigating or even preventing tragedies. Relationships are also actions and are not exempt from dangers of various kinds (emotional trauma, illness, violence, etc.). Sex education begins with the principles of a truly human relationship, where children and young people are educated so that they can not only protect themselves but also fulfill themselves as individuals.

One way to prevent this is to consider the personality of a potential partner as a decisive element, above their physical beauty or financial capacity, for example. This is why traditional morality imposes a series of restrictions and formalities on young people's relationships: the prohibition of more intimate contact before marriage or the need to ask parents for permission to date. Implicit in this was the idea that the individual must prove that their personality is trustworthy, that they possess sufficient self-control to endure abstinence, and that, therefore, they are not a puppet of their desires and emotions. Pornography contributes nothing to the formation of this awareness. On the contrary, it corrupts it fundamentally, encouraging and instigating the individual to base their relationships primarily on the physical attributes of their partner.

It is true that there are cases of individuals above suspicion who, after many years of relationship, were capable of betraying, deceiving, lying, or even assaulting and killing. This is not, however, a reason for society, with the approval of the State, to increase the risk of the dissemination of poor criteria for choosing relationships through pornography. It would be the same as suggesting the abolition of lifeguards because in many cases they were unable to save bathers from drowning. Let's acknowledge that if absolute effectiveness were a requirement for establishing preventive measures, then they would never be taken.

Therefore, if pornography does not contribute, but on the contrary, corrupts at its very foundation the reasonable values and criteria for establishing a good intimate relationship, making it extremely difficult for parents to provide this education, then it is only fair that the dissemination of such content be, at the very least, drastically restricted.

So I think that public (and private institutions ought to do what they can , in Brennan's words, to support parents in the discharge of their responsibilities '. So , warnings , ratings systems, restricted Access, requirements that children be accompanied by adults , all have their place where the access of minors to sexually oriented material is concerned . [...] Nudity in anything like a sexual context should , I think , be kept off television precisely because easy access by young people makes the already difficult task of relatives even more difficult . [...] Protecting the Young means making access to some such material more difficult for adults .³²

Pornography, aesthetically, mimics the annihilation of subjectivity as it occurs in the crime of rape, inducing the viewer to sexual pleasure based on reducing the other to their body, which is precisely the extreme violation of human dignity. If any moral judgment regarding rape is possible, then we must extend the same judgment to the art that mimics it: *accessio cedit principali* . If the crime is heinous, so too is the art that imitates and *glamorizes it*.

REFERENCES

BITENCOURT, Cezar Roberto. **Treatise on Criminal Law, Vol. 4** : Special Part. 3rd ed. São Paulo: Saraiva, 2008

BARROSO, Luís Roberto. **The Dignity of the Human Person in Contemporary Constitutional Law: Legal Nature, Minimum Contents and Application Criteria**. Provisional version for public debate. Mimeographed, December 2010.

CUNHA, Rogério Sanches. **Criminal Law – Special Part** . Vol. 3. 2nd ed. São Paulo: Revista dos Tribunais, 2009.

SHALAMÓV, Varlam . **Essays on the World of Crime** . São Paulo: Editora 34, 2016.

CUNHA, Rogério Sanches. **Criminal Law – Special Part**. Vol. 3. 2nd ed. São Paulo: Revista dos Tribunais, 2009.

DWORKIN, Ronald. **A Matter of Principle**. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 2001.

EBERSTADT, Mary; LAYDEN, Mary Anne. **The Social Costs of Pornography** . São Paulo: Quadrante, 2019.

³²GEORGE, Robert P. In *Defense of Natural Law*. Oxford: University Press, 2004, p. 192.

FAVORETTO, Affonso Celso. **Constitutional Criminal Principles**. São Paulo: Revista dos Tribunais, 2012.

FINNIS, John. **Reason and Passion : The Constitutional Dialectic of Free Speech and Obscenity** . Our Dame Law School Journal Articles , 1967.

_____. **Natural Law and Natural Rights**. São Leopoldo/RS: Unisinos , 2007.

FRAJHOF, Isabella Z. **Freedom of Expression and Pornography in the American Supreme Court**. Available at:
<http://www.pucrio.br/ensinopesq/ccpg/pibic/relatorio_resumo2011/Relatorios/CSS/DIR/DIR_Isabella%20Z.%20Frajhof.pdf> Accessed on 06/25/2020

GASSET, José Ortega y. **Essays on Aesthetics** (Mona Lisa, Three Paintings of Wine and Velázquez). São Paulo: Cortez, 2011.

GEORGE, Robert P. **In Defense of Natural Law**. Oxford: University Press, 2004.

HUNT, Lynn. **The Invention of Pornography: Obscenity and the Origins of Modernity 1500-1800**. São Paulo: Hedra , 1999.

GOMBRICH, EH. **The Story of Art**. Rio de Janeiro: LTC, 2013.

JONES, E. Michael. **Libido Dominandi – Sexual Liberation and Political Control**. Campinas/SP: Vide Editorial, 2019.

KIRK, Russel. **The Politics of Prudence** . São Paulo: É Realizações, 2014.

MONTEIRO, Ângelo. **Art or Disaster**. São Paulo: É Realizações, 2011.

NUCCI, Guilherme de Souza. **Annotated Penal Code**. 2nd ed. São Paulo: Revista dos Tribunais, 2002.

SCRUTON, Roger. **Beauty**. São Paulo: É Realizações, 2013.

_____. **Sexual Desire: a philosophical investigation**. Campinas/SP: Vide Editorial, 2016.

_____. **Thinkers of the New Left**. São Paulo: É Realizações, 2014.

WEAVER, Richard M. **Ideas Have Consequences** . São Paulo: É Realizações, 2016.

National Common Curricular Base. Available at:
<http://basenacionalcomum.mec.gov.br/images/BNCC_EI_EF_110518_-versaofinal_site.pdf>